

The Different Representations of the Coupling Constant Equation by the New Framework 8-Theory

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Abstract:

The following is an overview of the coupling constant equation in its five representations. The first and the original is the net variations of the manifold, which are prime numbers yielding a bosonic propagation. The second representation is the spin representation by using the prime critical line. The third representation is the arrow of time, the fourth is as a gauge field number predictor, and the last representation is the pi representation, and providing a testable prediction regarding the shape of the electron, to be to something aspiring a perfect circle.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

Used for describing the magnitudes of different interactions. We created the function of net variations $N(V)$ as a part of total variation pairs on a Lorentz manifold. We extrapolated the fine structure constant based on a previous element in the series:

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.1)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (2.2)$$

Second representation is the spin representation which was obtained after we pondered in regards to the meaning of The Invariant or "Majestic" (3) which appear in each term from the second element and above. We analyzed the equation on the "geometrical realm" and used the prime critical line. We reached the following representation:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3.1)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3.2)$$

In addition, from that representation, we were able to correlate the majestic (3) to spin. We saw that the terms inside the parenthesis are matter, which have spin one-half as a cause of destabilizing the cluster, the result is a net variation, outside of the parenthesis, also prime, and so together we have a probability for boson emission. We saw that from that representation that the weak interaction would differ in the nature of its spin since each term inside of the parenthesis is prime, excluding the weak interaction. It lacks two variations to reach the prime critical line. Therefore, we associated that to its left orientation. $27 < 29$.

Third representation is the arrow of time. In this representation we reasoned for the one sided arrow, and we saw that the Coupling constant series have a one sided direction. From strong amount of net Variations in infinitesimal amount, we are directed to larger amount of net variations divided by much larger clusters of total variations. In other words, we can reason why galaxies and cluster of galaxies can form only after the strong, weak and the electric. We are also able to reason the weakness Of gravity and the interactions in higher terms in the series.

$$1 > \frac{1}{30} > \frac{1}{128} > \frac{1}{850} \dots$$

We saw that the net variations growing much slower than the total variations. The net than is divided across the whole total, which indicate that immense clusters Of variations yield extremely weak forces within them.

$$\overrightarrow{1 > \frac{1}{30} > \frac{1}{128} > \frac{1}{850} \dots}$$

Forth representation is as a predictor of the number gauge fields. The most recent representation that correlates the right element within the parenthesis to the number of gauge bosons or gauge fields of the type of the interaction. Strong interaction has eight distinct gluon fields, in accordance to the eight.

$$\mathbf{8} + (1) \quad (5)$$

Weak interaction has three gauge fields – the W bosons and Z bosons. In accordance to right oriented three within the bracket, marked in green.

$$((8 * \mathbf{3}) + (3)) + 3 \quad (6)$$

Than we predict that there will be five gauge fields meditating electro-magnetism. It is a bold prediction, which need to be examined and could be completely wrong. However, risks must be taken in science, and that is a risky prediction.

$$((24 * \mathbf{5}) + (3)) + 5 \quad (7)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (\pi) \right) + N_V \quad (8)$$

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) : (24 + (\pi)) + 3 : (120 + (\pi)) + 5 : (840 + (\pi)) + 7 \dots \quad (9)$$

The pi representation. That is giving up certain accuracy on the coupling constant equation in order to get an insight regarding the shape of fermions. One is going to argue that such a representation is valid as we have a varying Lorenztion manifold, there could be a slight variations in the invariant three over time, toward pi and vice versa. In other words, the electron is not a perfect circle, but close to it. It is a varying circle, not a perfect shape. varying in physical theories could mean vibration. The fact that we have a varying framework allow us to dynamically allow such slight variations without being rigid, the fact that it is not pi, could be a positive indication. Perfect shape of a circle would be problematic in a final theory, but a varying, imperfect circle seems to be much more elegant and suitable to a framework of constant variation. So according to this representation, a boson will be emitted from something close to a perfect circle, which is the electron. We gave up certain amount of accuracy and reached an insight regarding the shape of an electron.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)